

A unified Cryptographic Framework for the Distribution of Quantum-Generated Keys

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Abstract—This work aims to make quantum-generated keys accessible to end users and integrate them into practical applications, enabling end-to-end secure communication across multiple interfaces. QKD and PQC are strategically implemented at various communication points to establish a unified, quantum-resistant cryptographic framework. QRNGs are central to this approach, generating high-entropy quantum keys and enabling their secure distribution without requiring specialised hardware. To address these objectives, an *Entropy-as-a-Service* architecture is introduced, providing end users with efficient and secure access to quantum key material. As a case study, this architecture is integrated into a group messaging application, showcasing its practicality and relevance for everyday communications.

I. INTRODUCTION

Quantum technologies have undergone rapid advancements in recent years. Among these, Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) enables two users to securely establish a shared cryptographic key through a quantum channel, ensuring that no eavesdropper can intercept the communication. QKD networks have been implemented and tested in various settings [1]–[3], yielding promising results. Additionally, Quantum Random Number Generators (QRNGs) [4], [5] offer a valuable tool by generating high-entropy key material, far surpassing the quality of classical pseudo-random number generators (PRNGs).

Despite these advancements, the practical adoption of QKD still faces significant challenges. Current implementations are limited to proof-of-concept systems, and the experimental nature and high cost of QKD devices make their widespread use by end users unlikely in the near future. Furthermore, the bandwidth and reliability limitations of QKD channels hinder their ability to fully replace existing security protocols and algorithms. These limitations, coupled with the growing threat posed by quantum computing, highlight the need for complementary technologies to safeguard security infrastructures. For instance, the advent of quantum computers threatens the integrity of well-established security protocols. Algorithms such as Shor’s algorithm could compromise widely used public-key cryptographic systems, which are critical for secure communications today. To address these risks, existing protocols must integrate new technologies designed to resist quantum computing capabilities. Beyond QKD, Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC) offers a promising solution, as it is

specifically designed to withstand threats posed by quantum computing. Its integration into security protocols is an active area of research.

Our approach addresses quantum-related vulnerabilities within the MACSec and IPsec protocols of the TCP/IP stack, which are particularly exposed to threats posed by advancing quantum computing technologies. These vulnerabilities arise from their dependence on public-key cryptographic algorithms for key exchange and authentication. Quantum attacks, particularly those leveraging Shor’s algorithm, can efficiently compromise these algorithms, exposing critical weaknesses in the security framework of these protocols. This highlights the importance of adopting quantum-resistant cryptographic solutions to ensure robust protection.

An *Entropy-as-a-Service* (EaaS) architecture is proposed, enabling end users to obtain QRNG-generated key material privately without the need for specialised equipment. To achieve this, the integration of PQC and QKD is suggested to establish quantum-resistant TCP/IP protocols, while providing secure and accessible high-entropy QRNG key material at the application layer. As a real-life functional use case, the architecture is integrated into a group messaging application to demonstrate its practicality and relevance for everyday communications. In summary, this work presents the following contributions:

- 1) **Link layer:** The EAP (Extensible Authentication Protocol) [6] is enhanced with PQC and QKD algorithms, replacing classical cryptographic counterparts to ensure secure key establishment within the MACSec suite [7].
- 2) **Network layer:** Two distinct solutions are proposed to integrate PQC and QKD into the IKEv2 (Internet Key Exchange version 2) [8] protocol. These solutions enhance the protection of shared keys utilized in the IPsec suite [9].
- 3) **Application layer:** A protocol is introduced for the private distribution of QRNG-generated keys to mobile devices. The EaaS architecture is defined, enabling clients to securely request high-entropy key material, which can be seamlessly incorporated into everyday communications.

II. BACKGROUND: PQC AND QKD

PQC is the natural evolution of classical cryptography to resist quantum attacks such as Shor's algorithm capable of breaking current public key algorithms such as RSA or Diffie-Hellman (DH) variants. It is based on mathematical problems that are difficult to solve and are implementable on today's computers, which is its major advantage. Apart from the signature algorithms, PQC stands out for the Key Encapsulation Mechanisms (KEM) that allow agreeing a shared secret between two members replacing DH. The main problem of PQC is the side-channel attack that takes advantage of implementation errors of algorithms in software or distribution. In addition, as in classical cryptography, there is the possibility of an attack that efficiently solves the problems on which they are based, making them vulnerable. In order to prevent these threats, NIST has created a standardization process [10], similar to the one carried out for AES or SHA. On the other hand, QKD algorithms rely on quantum mechanical principles such as superposition and entanglement to guarantee the security of cryptographic key transmission. The most notable algorithms within QKD based on superposition are BB84 and COW, both of which are already implemented in commercial solutions. E91 is widely used in research environments and is based on entanglement.

In contrast to PQC algorithms that operate in classical systems, QKD needs to be implemented in specific hardware in order to take advantage of quantum principles. This suggests that implementing QKD in real-world scenarios incurs higher costs compared to PQC. Additionally, QKD devices require direct connection via a quantum channel due to the absence of quantum repeaters, which restricts the maximum distance at which they can be separated. Nevertheless, the primary advantage of QKD over PQC is that the information transmitted in the former is ITS, which means that in the future there will be no attack in classical or quantum computing that will violate the QKD protocols.

III. LINK LAYER: MACSEC

MACsec (Media Access Control Security), defined in the IEEE 802.1AE standard, provides confidentiality, integrity, and source authentication in Ethernet networks through frame encryption, securing communication on point-to-point links within a local area network. MACsec operates just above the physical layer, making it a protocol suite that offers high speed and enhanced security, protecting not only the link layer but also the higher layers of the stack. Certain MACsec configurations are resistant to quantum computing attacks. For example, if a Pre-Shared Key (PSK) is used to generate the CAK (Connectivity Association Key), from which the encryption keys are derived, the communication remains secure. This is because only symmetric encryption mechanisms are used, which are still considered resistant to quantum attacks today. However, the main vulnerability lies in the key distribution process when using protocols such as EAP. For example, EAP-TLS, which uses asymmetric algorithms such as RSA or Diffie-Hellman (DH) for authentication and

the establishment of shared keys like the MSK (Master Session Key), is susceptible to attacks based on Shor's algorithm, which could compromise its security in a quantum computing environment.

To create quantum-safe MACsec, EAP must be reinforced. A solution is proposed to improve the EAP key exchange; the exchange method varies depending on the EAP method. In our solution, DH has been replaced in favor of PQC-KEMs and QKD algorithms. Moreover, in the authentication phase of EAP, which is carried out through a certificate exchange, the classic RSA algorithm is also replaced with a PQC solution. It is worth mentioning that at the time of writing this paper, no quantum signing algorithm exists; therefore, only PQC alternatives were available to improve EAP security. In practice, the PQC algorithms selected were CRYSTALS-Kyber and HQC as KEM and CRYSTALS-Dilithium, all of which are provided in the `LibOQS` library. Meanwhile, the available QKD hardware used was the *Cerberis QKD XGR System* developed by *ID Quantique*, which implements the COW (Coherent One Way) QKD protocol. Even though this solution is under development, the average QoS achieved with these algorithms was similar to that obtained with the classic MACsec version; therefore, a quantum-safe version of MACsec appears to be feasible in the near future.

IV. NETWORK LAYER: IPSEC

IPsec is a suite of security protocols that operates at Layer 3 (network layer). Its most widespread use is in Virtual Private Networks (VPNs), which enable end-to-end encrypted communication. In a post-quantum future, particular attention must be given to the first phase of IPsec: the IKEv2 protocol. During this initial phase, the shared cryptographic material is computed, serving as the seed for the second phase, where encrypted Security Associations (SA) are established. The most commonly used key exchange algorithms in IKEv2 are variants of Diffie-Hellman (DH), particularly those based on Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECDH). However, DH and ECDH are vulnerable to Shor's algorithm [11], implying that the IPsec suite itself becomes insecure in a quantum computing environment.

As one solution, it is proposed to adapt the IKEv2 protocol to use Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) as the key negotiation mechanism, ensuring that the derived cryptographic material is quantum-safe, thereby protecting IPsec. Figure 1 illustrates the message exchange between two users in an IPsec-QKD version. The diagram shows that the IKE messages remain unchanged, with the only modification occurring in the contents of the `IKE_SA_INIT` messages. In the classical version of IKE, regardless of the DH variant used, the *initiator* and *responder* exchange public key information, referred to as `KEi` and `KEr`, respectively, in the figure.

In the QKD-based version, both participants, Alice and Bob, have access to a Key Management Entity (KME), which manages the keys for a QKD node. These nodes must be directly connected via a quantum channel to distribute QKD keys. KMEs typically implement interfaces defined by ETSI,

Fig. 1. IKEv2 with QKD as key exchange.

such as 014 or 004 [12], [13]. To integrate QKD keys into IKE, the *initiator* must first send a request to its KME, obtaining a QKD key (Key_i) along with its corresponding Key ID (Key_ID_i). The *initiator* then sends the first IKE_SA_INIT message, replacing the DH public key with the received Key ID. The responder replies with its own IKE_SA_INIT message, but omits the public key field, leaving it empty. The *initiator* then generates the first IKE_AUTH message, using the QKD key for encryption. At this point, the *responder* must send a request to its KME with the received Key ID to retrieve the shared QKD key. The *responder* uses this key to authenticate the *initiator*'s IKE_AUTH message and generates its own IKE_AUTH message. Finally, the *initiator* authenticates the *responder*, thereby completing Phase 1 of IPsec-QKD.

Alternatively, instead of using QKD, we integrate PQC into IKEv2 to achieve IPsec-PQC. In this case, the message exchange remains the same as described in RFC 5996, but with the public information of DH replaced. In the first IKE_SA_INIT , sent by the *initiator*, KE_i contains the public key of a PQC-KEM key pair generated by the *initiator*. After receiving this message, the *responder* generates a random secret using a QRNG and encapsulates it with the public key (KE_r), obtaining the parameter KE_r to be included in the second IKE_SA_INIT message. This way, the *initiator* will be able to decapsulate KE_r with its private key, and both the *initiator* and *responder* share a quantum-safe secret ready to encrypt the tunnel in the second phase of IPsec-PQC.

V. EAAS AND INSTANT MESSAGING

In this layer, EaaS allows end users to access QRNG key material without requiring specialised equipment so that they can integrate it into existing protocols. As QRNGs are expensive and it is impractical to include them into portable devices, a method for end users to access this high entropy source is required. To this end we propose an EaaS architecture: through it, users are able to request key material to a server with access to a QRNG in a private manner. Our EaaS architecture is based on the *Privacy-Preserving Key Transmission Protocol* defined in [14]. In it, Users interact with two logical entities: the Authentication Server (AS) and the Proof Validation Server. In practice, they can be implemented either as a single or separate services. The two entities possess some information

Fig. 2. Design of an Entropy-as-a-Service (EaaS) architecture.

in common: a Merkle Tree, which the AS populates and the PVS uses to verify proofs.

The communication between Users and the servers is divided into two phases: Authentication and Key Request. In the former, the User provides identifying information (e.g. a digital certificate) to the Authentication Server. If successful, the AS authorises the User to perform the next step. In the Key Request phase, Users present a *Zero-Knowledge Succinct Non-Interactive Argument of Knowledge* (zk-SNARK) proof demonstrating that they have previously performed the Authentication Step. Crucially, it is impossible to link the zk-SNARK to the credential the User presented to authenticate.

a) EaaS Architecture: Our proposed EaaS architecture is shown in Figure 2. It inherits the server structure and communication steps from the Privacy-Preserving Key Transmission Protocol of [14]. The EaaS platform is structured as a centralised service with multiple *Local Branches*, as shown in Figure 2: both the AS and PVS are located in a *Remote Service* where common information is stored and the QRNG is accessible. In each of the *Local Branches*, a device known as *Local Provider* acts as intermediary with the Remote Service.

The Authentication phase unfolds as follows: The User first presents authentication information to the AS, which checks a User Database to verify its validity and apply access control policies. If successful, the AS will authorise the user to perform the Key Request step. In addition to authentication information, the User also sends to the server some *Quality of Service* that it expects to receive, like key size, minimum entropy or expiration time. The AS will then validate that the User is authorised to request said properties by checking the User Database, in which the access control policies for each User are specified. These policies will depend on an agreement between clients and the EaaS provider. The execution of the Key Request Step between Users and the Proof Validation Server is mediated by a Local Provider, which acts as an intermediary. This device is located in the local branch and communicates with the User through Near Field Communication (NFC). The Local Provider forwards all information provided by the User and the responses from the PVS.

Fig. 3. Overview of EaaS integration into group messaging applications.

b) *Communication channels:* . To communicate with the PVS, the Local Provider is equipped with a traditional link and a quantum link. Remarkably, the Local Provider acts solely as an intermediary and does not retain or store any information; its sole function is to facilitate the secure data exchange between the mobile application and the PVS. The current configuration establishes a point-to-point connection between the Local Provider and the PVS, necessitating that the Local Provider remains at a fixed location. The quantum channel between the Local Provider and the PVS allows these two parties to execute QKD protocols. When the Local Provider receives the random bytes, uses NFC to send the key to the final user’s mobile for secure storage. We note that any information other than the QRNG key that is transmitted between the Local Provider and the PVS employs the traditional link, as they are not required to be kept in secret. This limits the use of the quantum channel to those tasks that could benefit to its level of security. As mentioned, the Local Provider also communicates with the User through NFC, which requires the User to be physically located at one of the branches. The use of both NFC and QKD channels for the final transmission of the QRNG key ensures that this value remains in secret through all steps of the process.

c) *Application to Instant Messaging:* We demonstrate the applicability of our EaaS solution to everyday communications by proposing its integration into a group messaging application. In these structures, all members of the group share a common secret key that they use to encrypt messages between them. A high-level overview of our proposal is shown in Figure 3. First, users request QRNG key material from the EaaS platform following the protocol described above. Then, they generate a key pair from the obtained randomness and use it to join a messaging group. Periodically, users introduce new entropy into the shared secret by consuming segments of the obtained QRNG key material. To that end, we employ the *Messaging Layer Security (MLS)* protocol, recently standardised in RFC 9420 [15]. By injecting the QRNG key material obtained through the execution of the EaaS protocol, we delegate to MLS the tasks of generating identities, joining groups, and updating the shared key material.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This work introduces an EaaS framework for securely distributing quantum-generated keys. The framework integrates Quantum Key Distribution and Post-Quantum Cryptography across different layers of the Internet protocol stack to achieve end-to-end quantum-resistant security. Quantum Random Number Generators generate high-entropy keys, which are securely distributed to end users through the EaaS architecture. Above it, the Messaging Layer Security protocol demonstrates the applicability of this solution in group messaging applications, ensuring secure key updates and dynamic cryptographic functionality for everyday communications.

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